

AN ASSESSMENT OF “KABALIKAT SA KABUHAYAN” PROGRAM ON FARMERS IN DAVAO CITY

GENE ANTHONY S. SALAZAR

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6861177>

Published Date: 19-July-2022

Abstract: This study, aimed to develop an enhancement program metrics framework. The study used descriptive-comparative research design. An online survey questionnaire consisting of 30 items was used to collect data from 72 recipient farmers of the program in Davao City. Mean and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were the statistical tools used in the study. The results of the study revealed that the level of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program was high in terms of attainment of program objectives, participation of agencies, and capacity building. The study found out that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation when group according to socio-demographic profile. Lastly, the enhancement program metrics framework is called “Kabuhayang Angat Sa Pilipinas” Program. The enhancement program metrics framework consists of five Key Result Areas namely: Training and Course Management, Financial Literacy and Management, Entrepreneurship and Capacity Building Seminar, Basic Business Plan and Proposal Techniques, and Learning Integration and Immersion.

Keywords: Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan Program, Attainment of Program Objectives, Capacity Building, Educational Attainment, Employment, Enhancement Program, Participation of Agencies, and Years in Farming.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The insufficient attention and efforts given in a program leading to a failure evaluation underly on the factors as high concentration on the technical details, vague accountability performance indicators and measurement, inconsistent process management implementation, lack of manpower motivation in achieving optimal results and insufficient provision of trainings, project tools and techniques needed for the team. A study conducted in United States, project failures were attributed to 43% of poor communication while 42% contributed to poor process factors and 32% attributed to people factors (Discenza & Forman, 2013).

Hence, program design, program monitoring and program evaluation are the integral parts of project management. These integrated components will enable to manage the resources and activities to improve development plans from short-term to long-term impact that linked chain of results: input will result to output that catalyze outcomes which will give beneficial impacts. (International Labour Organization, 2021).

Moreover, in the Philippines the National Economic Development Authority (NEDA) and Department of Budget and Management (DBM) issued a Joint Memorandum Circular No. 2015-01 entitled “National Evaluation Policy Framework of the Philippines”. This policy framework was crafted to provide parameters on the conduct of assessment and evaluations among government agencies that provide strong support in public governance, public accountability, public transparency, and to come-up with an evidence-based output for a sound public decision making. However, in the study of Asian Development Bank (2018), there were 63 completed and evaluated projects from 2003 to 2016 resulted to some identified key failures such as zero target for inclusive poor planning and incompetent assessment tools used in the local implementing units (National Economic Development Authority and Department of Budget and Management, 2015).

The “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program was started in 2006 by the patriarch of SM Group of Companies, Mr. Henry Sy, Sr. which aims to teach a sustainable project that will emphasize on raising the quality of living standards among small farmers. The main highlight of the 12-week long training program is to introduce and teach comprehensive courses in organic farming, financial literacy, sustainability plan immersion and presentation, and marketing and linkages of their commodities. As of 2018, there are 23,170 recipient farmers who graduated from the program (SM Foundation Incorporated, 2018).

Meanwhile, program implementation and evaluation become failure because objectives and goals are lack of supporting details, some areas do not address the critical issues, details are unrealistic, lack of performance metrics and the influence of bureaucratic control and administration (Charvat, 2013). A comprehensive description of a program activations may include necessary data on the processes, links and phases of an expected results as well as addressing the challenges encountered in the implementation stage. The output in the assessment phase shall coincide with the nature, timing, side effects, patterns in the changes encountered and its significant relationship in the outcomes (Sharpe, 2011).

There is a sense of urgency in conducting this study for there is a need to determine the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program through assessing its components based on socio-demographic profile, attainment of its objectives, participation of agencies, capacity building, and creating an enhancement program metrics framework based on the findings of the study.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to assess the “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program on farmers in Davao City. Particularly, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Educational attainment;
 - b. Years in farming; and
 - c. Employment?
2. What is the level of implementation of the “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program, in terms of:
 - a. Attainment of program objectives;
 - b. Participation of agencies; and
 - c. Capacity building?
3. Is there a significant difference in the implementation of the “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when the respondents are grouped by:
 - a. Educational attainment;
 - b. Years in farming; and
 - c. Employment?
4. What enhancement program can be developed based on the framework?

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study would be beneficial to the following stakeholders:

Department of Agriculture. This would serve as the catalyst in strengthening partnerships with Department of Agriculture thru City Agriculture’s Office, to boost operations towards food security and sustainability which shall focus on small communities.

Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). This would serve as the benchmark in the improvement of the delivery of services to small scale farmers and marginalized individuals.

SM Foundation Incorporated. This would benefit them by conceptualizing framework which shall aid in improving the operation of the existing program through maximizing the agricultural sectors such as dairy farming, swine farming, and cattle farming.

Farmers. This would serve as farmers' guiding principles in sustainability and empowerment. In addition, this study will give a baseline data on future farmer's program planning and management.

Future researchers. This would serve a significant reference and literature on their study.

Scope and Limitation

This research activity focuses on the lens of assessing the level of implementation of "*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*" Program on farmers in Davao City. An online survey questionnaire with 30 items was used to facilitate data gathering from March 2020 until December 2020. There are 72 "*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*" Program respondents on this study.

Definition of Terms

The following are defined by the researcher according on how they are operationally used in this study.

Attainment of Program Objectives. These are the defined step by step process to attain the goal(s) of a certain project, program, or policy. Moreover, the direct target of the defined objectives will help the administrator facilitate assessment on the factors, may it be positive or negative, that enables in mobilizing the program.

Capacity Building. This refers to an essential aspect of a project, program, or policy where in the participants are given an opportunity to acquire, learn, apply, embody, and replicate the educational course design of a program.

Educational attainment. This refers on the extent or degree of education obtained by the farmer.

Employment. This is defined as the type of work, industry, and organization the farmer belongs to earn for a living.

Enhancement program. This refers to the streamlining and redefining the distinct features and characteristics of program design and to incorporate another recommended program design that is tailor fit to its recipients.

***Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan* Program.** This is a livelihood program of SM Foundation where the farmers will undergo a comprehensive 12-week training. This was founded in 2006 by the late Mr. Henry Sy, Sr. where he envisioned an empowered and sustainable small farmer through this program. In 2018, there were 23,170 graduates from the program.

Participation of Agencies. This refers to the distinct characteristic in terms of participation that involves agencies that is significant in mobilization of a program.

Years in farming. This focuses on the extent or length of farming experience by the farmer and how the farmer applies his personal learnings and can contribute also in return to the general knowledge of the program.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter discusses the review of literature and studies, theory base, conceptual framework, and hypothesis of the study.

Related Literature and Studies

The related literature and studies mentioned in this study provide a comprehensive background and support on the level of implementation of programs in local and international context. Also, these serves as a reference of the researcher in better comprehension and deepening on the variables given.

Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan

This is a program of SM Foundation Incorporated initiative enables empowerment of small farmers. It was founded by Mr. Henry Sy, Sr. in 2006. The program recipients reached to 23,170 in 2018. Moreover, the SM Supermalls submits a letter of intent to various partner agencies such as City Agriculture Office, Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), Technical Skills and Development Authority (TESDA), Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), Cooperative Development Authority (CDA) and other private sectors for integration and coordination.

There will be 100 participants for the program. These participants may be composed of both professional, skilled and non-professional individuals that will go through the 12-week course. There are experts from various agencies as the key lecturers on various program course outlines. After the completion, the participants shall graduate and will receive certification (SM Foundation Incorporated, 2018).

Socio-Demographic Profile. According to (Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, 2019), socio-demographic profiles or characteristics comprise of age, gender, educational background, ethnic and racial background, religion, marital status, professional or career experiences, aggregate monthly family income and employment status. These details are commonly used to best define target samples and to analyze sampling margin of error.

Moreover, the advantage of measuring socio-demographic profile gives a clear background in measuring, analyzing, and interpreting individual social and demographical characteristics. The importance of knowing the socio-demographic profile because the government, private organizations, non-government organizations and other institutions may learn the behavioral pattern of the population and these patterns may be gathered and used for policy development and economic market study (Hayes, 2021).

Attainment of Program Objectives. A study of Crano, W.D. et al., (2014) stated that the qualifications on effective evaluation are the following: the goals and objectives of the program must be specified by the program implementers that allows a more definable and quantifiable outcomes; the features of the program must be distinct and well-rounded in identifying whether the program is present or absent in particular scenario and time; regardless of the presence or absence of the treatment program is important and valid also in assessment of the final outcomes.

Furthermore, a program implementation must be workable program. These encompass person's involvement, the program design, the location and how it will be implemented and mobilized. It shows the quality of an implementation that plays a major role in bringing up the results or the outcomes. Implementation science is a logical process for the implementation of programs and practices that indicate empirical evidence from the research field in order to suggest that the program and practices are replication worthy (United States Department of Health and Human Services, 2021).

On the other hand, (Durlak, 2013) defines program implementation as a manner of execution in which a proposed program or initiative is placed into action and provides an essential part on the establishment of internal, external, contrive, and data statistics that may infer validity and reliability of outcome evaluations.

A study of (Charvat, 2013) suggested that the program must have the following criteria, and these include the following; it should have a beginning and ending dates and scheduled activities; has a detailed cost planning, coordination, manpower planning, and quality assessment checklists; it is a unique success, and it comprises risks, threats, challenges, or failures; and has a certain level of implementation that needs to activate. In addition, to fully attain the program objective it must have a better comprehension and intensive preparation on the needs of the stakeholders as the core foundation in order to continuously improve the processes that requires a systematic assessment and evaluation. Taking into these considerations of challenges the program execution will aid to develop a sound and relatively SMART program in future time (Rogers, 2020).

Participation of Agencies. The main concept of participation of agencies revolves in the stakeholder's theory. This theory focuses on the organization on how to widen scope with critical attention in decision making that includes not only the shareholders, but also the inclusion of the interests of the clients, employees, goods and services, suppliers, communities, and the society. The stakeholder theory is an appropriate business framework to help strategize intensification of the worth and value of the organization by means of taking a high priority on the interest of all the stakeholders, both internal and external, given a high importance on the distinct role of agencies (Freeman, 2012).

Furthermore, public participation is essential. It is defined as not a single spearheaded event, but a collective series of activities and actions by agencies over the full lifespan of a project or program to announce and disseminate information to the public and could collect valuable inputs from them (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2018).

According to (Kessler, 2014), stakeholder participation improves work compliance because actors involved are more knowledgeable, committed, and supportive on the over-all program procedures. Another factor is when designing a stakeholder participatory approaches, the capacity of all the actors should be carefully take into consideration in terms of time, financial resources, manpower involvement, and training and expertise so that these will not hinder the entire flow.

The National Economic Development Authority (2017) stated that the over-all thrust of the PDP 2017-2022 framework is to build a future where every Filipino citizen enjoys a *matatag, maginhawa at panatag na buhay*. The main pillar of interest under PDP 2017-2022 framework emphasizes on "Inequality-Reducing Transformation" or the so-called "*Pagbabago*". This pillar looks after in economic accessibility and convenience for the marginalized subsectors and

groups of people in the over-all economic participation towards progress. Its main goal is to expand the economic opportunities in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries.

The Department of Agriculture targets a “food-secure Philippines with prosperous farmers and fisherfolks”. To attain the target of the agency, it must collectively empower both public and private sectors to increase high productivity level and efficiency in agriculture and in return, it equates to a profitability and sustainable livelihood by integrating sustainability, competitiveness, and resiliency on technological and indigenous practices. The “New Thinking of Agriculture” principles include modernization of agriculture; industrialization of agriculture; promotion of exports; farm consolidation; infrastructure development; roadmap development; higher budget and development for agriculture; and legislative support (Department of Agriculture, 2021).

The vision of Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) is to attain freedom from hunger and poverty, equal accessibility on opportunities moved by a fair, just, and harmonious society for all Filipino people. Its mission is to be a leader in formulation, implementation, and coordination on the core social welfare services and to develop policies and programs directed to the poor, vulnerable and underprivileged Filipinos (Department of Social Welfare and Development, 2021).

The SM Foundation Incorporated (2018) reported that there are 23,170 beneficiary farmers on the “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program, 187 farmers’ training sessions had been accomplished to date and 2,925 barangays in 772 municipalities and cities. They serve as catalyst and impact for change in the communities where they operate and serve. Their main goal to a sustainable growth path is to revitalize and energize local economies.

Capacity Building. In the study of United Nations Development Program (2016), capacity building is described as a part of capacity development where the core principle of people empowerment is realized when their full potential is harness for being sustainable and economic viable and replicated in the long run. The following core values in relation to capacity building: integrate, coordinate, and monitor skills development programs; restructure efforts to promote and develop middle-level manpower; approve skills standards and tests; develop an accreditation system for institutions involved in the middle-level manpower development; fund programs and projects for technical education and skills development; assist trainers training program (Technical Education and Skills Development, 2018).

Furthermore, the four integrated components of capacity building are the following: institutional development, human resource development, financial resource development and an effective national society program. On the institutional development, key factors to be considered herewith are corporate identity, legal background, governance, integrity, and strategic planning. While financial development factors are fund-raising initiatives and other sources of revenue generation. On the other hand, human resources development includes management, manpower complements such as volunteers, board members and staff, and learning and development capacity. Lastly, an effective national program should comprise identified program and services, program assessment, project management, program monitoring and evaluation and capacity building as an evident-based action (International Committee of the Red Cross, 2020).

Moreover, Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (2020) program encourages a full and active participation and industry mobilization and integration among labor agency, local government units and technical-vocational agencies in the skills development to leverage Philippine’s manpower human and work force. Also, TESDA describes community-based training as a primordial in addressing the poor and marginalized sectors which are incapacitated to access formal training provisions.

It purposively acts as a design to mobilize the creation of livelihood enterprises that shall be implemented. Moreover, it also provides linkages to assist partner agencies such as local government units (LGUs), non-governmental organizations (NGOs), people organizations and other organizations that aim to help marginalized people to access productive venues to be sustainable, empowered, and capable for themselves and for their communities (Technical Education and Skills Development Authority, 2020).

Significant Difference in the Level of Implementation of Program

Educational Attainment. In a study conducted by United Nations Educational, Scientific, Cultural and Cultural Organization Institute of Statistics (2021) in Asia, educational attainment is used to track the rate of adults aged 25 years and above who have fully completed the stages of education as qualified by the International Standard Classification of Education beginning primary level to doctoral level.

However, in the Philippines the Department of Education was mandated to formulate, implement, and coordinate policies, plans, programs, and projects in the areas of formal and non-formal basic education. It supervises all elementary and secondary education institutions, including alternative learning systems, both public and private; and provides for the establishment and maintenance of a complete, adequate, and integrated system of basic education relevant to the goals of national development (Department of Education, 2020). While, the Commission on Higher Education was mandated to provide a world-class Filipino graduates and work force with international standards benchmark in tertiary education (Commission on Higher Education, 2021).

According to United Nations Educational, Scientific, Cultural and Cultural Organization Institute of Statistics (2020), educational attainment is defined as the highest stage of education that a person has obtained. This is the reason why educational attainment is one of the indicators in the SDG Target 4.4 and the highest educational obtained also equates on the better health and living lifestyle, exposure on civic engagements, minimized violence and crime rate, among others. The International Panel on Social Progress (2021) states that education is an appraised asset for it improves socio-cultural dimensions in terms of religion, personal identity, professional skills, citizenship, human capabilities, and social prestige. Education is an instrument to mobilize social progress.

Years in Farming. In the National Geographic (2020) article, it discussed the historical account of farming and agriculture dated back when ancient civilizations and people were used to hunt animals and get wild plants. The past 11,500 years, people eventually acquired the learning on how to grow cereals and various root crops, thus, they became dependent on farming life. Moreover, rice and corn have been coined as the first locally grown crops and ancient Chinese people used to grow these crops in 7500 BCE.

In the “International Standard Classification of Occupations”, farming is defined as a person who generally owns and manages their own farmland. Moreover, farmer can operationally perform management functions related to agricultural productions and planning systems. On other hand, subsistence farming is an activity where some farm commodities are harvested and sold for income. In addition, subsistence farming means rural employment with a goal to provide socio-economic livelihood and a unit of analysis in crafting labor market policies the (International Labour Office Statistics, 2012).

Employment. International Labour Office (2020) glossary of statistical terms defines persons in employment “as all those of working age who, during a short reference period, were engaged in any activity to produce goods or provide services for a pay or profit.” This encompasses person “at work” who works for a job in an hour and employed individual “not at work” due to momentary absence from the job, or to a working time arrangements examples are work shifting, in flexible time, compressed work week and leave compensation benefit for a given period. On the other hand, there is a relationship between employment and poverty that may influence the underlying factors. Thus, the growth in employment on top of its productivity can accelerate the growth rate of the economy (Khan, 2013).

Government Employee. The Civil Service Commission (CSC) is legally mandated by the constitution in promotion of morale, efficiency, integrity, responsiveness, progressiveness, and courtesy in the Civil Service. The CSC is the governing agency of all the public officials and employees (Civil Service Commission, 2014).

Private Employee. The Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) is the governing body under Presidential Decree No. 442, a decree creating a Labor Code as a primary labor law of the Republic of the Philippines. The main goal on the creation of the Labor Code of the Philippines is to promote social justice and equality where labor laws are for the humanization and equalization of socio-economic factors of the State that ultimately in effect, to protect and safeguard the rights and welfare of the Filipino work force. This is a vehicle that promises the order, safety, health, equity, morals, and general welfare of the Filipino communities (Department of Labor and Employment, 2017).

Self-Employed. According to Murray (2020), self-employed any individuals who are working for themselves only, without any employee-employer relationship and does not own shares or stocks of any corporation. Moreover, self-according to Internal Revenue Service, one qualifies as self-employed if he engages in sole-proprietorship or independent contracting; a member of a partnership that brings on a business name; and someone who engages business for their livelihood, that includes part-time work.

In the Philippines, the Bureau of Internal Revenue mandated to regulate taxation, which includes self-employed persons who receives an income from the activity of business or trade and/or practice of one’s profession. In addition, purely self-

employed individuals and professionals with a gross receipts/sales and other non-operating income which do not exceed the threshold amount of 3 million pesos, the taxpayer has the two options: first, 8% income tax on gross sales/receipts more than 250,000.00 in replacement of the graduated tax rates and percentage tax; second, payment of tax based on the graduated income tax (Bureau of Internal Revenue, 2019).

Enhancement Program. In the study of Food and Agriculture Organization United Nations (2018), global food and agriculture trend to date, stands critically. Although, from the past decades, global food productivity has been registered significantly high that made to feed up the never-ending increasing world population. Moving forward, the right direction towards in an inclusive abundance and to end the problem in food scarcity and security is clearly inked by the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. This agenda will surpass the complexity of the struggles and challenges the world faces, which requires a transformative action, embracing the frameworks of sustainability and evaluate the root causes of poverty so that no person will be left behind. To bridge the gap of people and the planet, food and agriculture can aid to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals in 2030.

In this perspective, transformative policies and programs must be grounded on the solid trends and its root cause analysis on the baseline such as high population growth and urbanization, natural resources scarcity due to competition, climate change, state and local conflicts and crises, natural calamities, food instability, and crops pest infestations and diseases. Thus, the fundamental principle on the delivery of sustainable food and agriculture is the creation of participative and inclusive policy that integrates the roles and responsibilities of societal sectors, stakeholders, and government agencies. Adaptation of governance to the new challenges are enhancement of policy making and development thru a dialogue and coordination; strengthening innovation systems; adapting and improving of financial investments to support mobilization of the program/policy; strengthens the enabling environment and reformation and enhancement of the institutional framework (Food and Agriculture Organization United Nations, 2018).

The International Labor Organization (2021) discussed that project evaluation is a systematic methodology and objective assessment of any ongoing or completed project and program. The main purpose is to find out the pertinence and the level of achievement of project objectives, development effectiveness, project delivery efficiency, its impact, and its sustainability. Also, evaluation inputs the on-ground challenges and lessons learned in the implementation process and acts as an integrated part of stakeholders' decision-making.

The related literatures give sufficient comprehension related to the variables of the study. It supports the researcher in the verification of the theories and the interpretation in composing of the survey questionnaires. Moreover, it provides data pertaining to the assessment of "*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*" Program in Davao City.

Theory Base

The theoretical lens of the study espouses the Program Theory of Sidani and Sechrest (1999) which consists of the set of statements that describe a particular program, which explains its why, what, when, where, who and how. This also includes the predictability of the outcomes of the program, and the specifications of the requirements needed to have a desired program output and outcomes. The program should have its own defined objectives to be achieved that encompasses its nature and problem, the target participants, the timing of its planning and implementation, the target location, and the desired output and outcome to measure and assess.

In addition, the proposition of Prosovac and Carey (1997) suggested that a program theory gives a baseline data for the evaluation of relatively uncontrolled programs. Specifications of the program theory to its actors will guide and assist stakeholders to responsibly carry out their roles and responsibilities while elaborating how they manage the financial aspect of the program.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrated in Figure 1 shows the variables of the study. The independent variable is the implementation of "*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*" Program with the following indicators: attainment of program objectives, participation of agencies and capacity building. The moderator variables are educational attainment, years in farming and employment. Lastly, the enhancement program metrics framework is formulated based on the results of the study.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework showing the variables of the study.

Hypothesis

The following alternative hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is a significant difference in the implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program, when the respondents are grouped according to educational attainment, years in farming, and employment.

3. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, sources of data, data gathering instrument, sampling technique, step-by-step procedures, and statistical treatment of the study.

Research Design

The research study employed descriptive-comparative research design. A descriptive-comparative research design is used to attempt in validating conclusions beyond a singular scenario and it also explains the likelihood or differences among objects of analysis and its relationship among the objects versus their conditional qualifications (Esser & Vliegthart, 2017). The analysis of variance or ANOVA is a test to determine whether there are significant differences between the means of three or more independent and non-related groups (Laerd Statistics, 2018).

Source of Data

The study used primary data to collect important information. According to Hamilton (2012), primary sources of data are unique materials on which research is based. These data are first-hand testimony or direct evidence concerning a topic under consideration. The survey questionnaire was based on the project briefer of the program. It was prepared by the researcher, validated by the panel committee, and distributed to respondents thru online due to restrictions on face-to-face interview. There are 72 farmer respondents of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program in Davao City.

Data Gathering Instrument. To mobilize the data gathering of the study, a 30-item survey questionnaire was drafted for the target group of participants. In this view, the survey questionnaire was patterned in SM Foundation’s “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Project Briefer. Moreover, the survey questionnaire was tested in terms of validity test and reliability test before the conduct of the study. Below are the scale, interval, level, and interpretation parameters of the survey questionnaire:

Scale	Interval	Level	Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Very High	If the item stated is always observed and performed.
4	3.50-4.49	High	If the item stated is often observed and performed.
3	2.50-3.49	Moderate	If the item stated is sometimes observed and performed.
2	1.50-2.49	Low	If the item stated is seldom observed and performed.
1	1.00-1.49	Very Low	If the item stated is none or never observed and performed.

Participants in the validation phase were selected SM City Davao Mall Administration employees and distinguished University of the Southeastern Philippines College of Development Management professors. Due to the public health restrictions brought about COVID19, the researcher opted to have an online survey. It is a method used to distribute the survey instrument thru an online medium targeted the respondents of the study (Torrentira, 2020; Sy et al., 2020).

Sampling Technique

The respondents of this study were 72 graduates of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program from 2015 to 2019 in Davao City. The researcher used snowball sampling as a primary source of data through an online survey. Frey (2018) states that a snowball technique is a sampling technique used to gather several respondents in the study by means of referrals by a person who has the same characteristics or qualifications of research interest in the target population.

The study targeted Davao City due to its population and geographical location which is in the southeastern part of the Philippines. Hence, it is known to be the largest city in terms of land area. The city is divided into three congressional districts and segmented into eleven administrative districts with 182 barangays. Moreover, Davao City is recognized as a large-scale agricultural city, and agriculture is on the top priority list of investment based on Davao City Investment Incentive Code. To date, the inventory level of the vegetable crops in terms of land area is 1,215 hectares, eyeing potential in the attainment of food security and sustainability. (Davao City Investment Promotion Center, 2021).

Meanwhile, the 72 respondent-participants were “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program graduates and residents of Davao City. There were 33 respondents from Baguio District, Davao City; 13 respondents from Los Amigos, Davao City; 10 respondents from Barangay Cadallian, Davao City; 8 respondents from Barangay Carmen, Davao City; 5 respondents from Lanang, Davao City; 2 respondents from Barangay Talandang, Davao City; and 1 respondent from Marilog District, Davao City. These respondents were eligible to participate in the said study since they graduated from the “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program from 2015-2019, local residents of Davao City, and voluntarily participated in the study. However, personalities who do not qualify on the aforementioned inclusion criteria were not permitted to be part of this study.

Procedure of the Study

The first stage of conceptualizing the research study is thru identification of the problem or the gap. The variables were critically chosen based on the given literatures of some authors that best fit to the study. After critically choosing the variables, a conceptual framework is set where specific questions are asked about the problem. The relationship of independent and dependent variables was inferred in line to the conceptual framework. The questions were based on the “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program Briefer. The instrument was submitted to the thesis advisory committee which was subjected for evaluation and validation. As soon as the research instrument was validated, distribution to target participants was conducted. Due to the state of public health emergency brought by COVID19, the data collection was

done thru an online survey. The convenience and snowball sampling techniques were used to expedite the entire data gathering procedures. Finally, when the survey questionnaires were retrieved, the responses were processed through tabulation, analysis, and interpretation using the right statistical tools.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were administered in the processing, analyzing, and interpreting of data.

Mean. This was used in determining level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program on farmers in Davao City in terms of attainment of program objectives, participation of agencies and capacity building.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used to test if there was significant difference in the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when respondents are grouped by highest educational attainment, years in farming, and employment.

4. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program, and its significant relationship when respondents are grouped according to educational attainment, years in farming, and employment. Also, it presents the enhancement program through matrix framework.

Socio-Demographic Profile

Shown in Table 1 below are the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment, years in farming and employment.

Educational Attainment. There were 2 respondents under elementary level/graduate, 22 respondents who were high school level/graduate, and, 48 respondents who were college level/graduate. This means that majority of the respondents were college level/graduate.

Years in Farming. In terms of years in farming, 69.44% of the respondents have 1-10 years in farming, 15.28% of the respondents are comprised of 11 to 20 years in farming, and, 15.28% is composed of 20 years and above years in farming. This implies that majority of the respondents have 1-10 years in farming experience.

Employment. In terms of employment, 22.23% is comprised of government employees, while 33.33% is composed of private employees. On the other hand, 44.44% belongs to respondents who were self-employed. This infers that majority of the respondents were self-employed.

Over-all, this resonates the importance of the study on socio-demographic profile as stated by Hayes (2021) that the data collected, analyzed and interpreted may give a baseline data on the population behavior and bases for crafting policy development plan and economic enhancement research analysis.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents.

Socio-Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Level/Graduate	2	2.77
High School Level/Graduate	22	30.56
College Level/Graduate	48	66.67
Total	72	100
Years in Farming		
1-10 Years	50	69.44
11-20 Years	11	15.28
20 Years and above	11	15.28
Total	72	100
Employment		
Government	16	22.23
Private	24	33.33
Self-Employed	32	44.44
Total	72	100

Level of Implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program

Presented in Table 2 below are the levels of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program in terms of attainment of program objectives, participation of agencies, and capacity building. The indicator on Attainment of Program Objectives has a mean of 4.17 with a standard deviation of 0.70. The level of implementation is high, while Participation of Agencies is tabulated with a mean of 3.95 with a standard deviation of 0.93. The level of implementation is high. Also, Capacity Building scores a mean of 4.29 with a standard deviation of 0.74. The level of implementation is high. As shown in table 1, the overall level of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program, has a total mean of 4.14 with a standard deviation of 0.74, which results to a high level of implementation.

Table 2. Level of Implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Attainment of Program Objectives	0.70	4.17	High
Participation of Agencies	0.93	3.95	High
Capacity Building	0.74	4.29	High
Overall	0.74	4.14	High

The result corroborates with the study of International Labour Organization (2021) that the over-all program evaluation assesses the planning, integrating, and managing the future effect done during a program cycle, and because project and program are collaborative efforts, the partners have a co-shared responsibility to carry out the initiatives towards attainment of goals, outcomes and create impact. Also, in the study of Durlak (2013), it stated that the level of implementation of program necessitates thorough and comprehensive planning, inclusion of various stakeholders and procedures that strengthen accountability and reliability.

Attainment of Program Objectives. It is presented in Table 2.1 the level of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program, in terms of attainment of program objectives. The result tells that the level of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program in terms of attainment of program objectives scored a total mean of 4.17 which resulted to a high level of implementation. The result infers that there are some aspects of the attainment of program objectives that need to be re-assessed and be improved.

Table 2.1. Level of Implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program interms of Attainment of the Program Objectives.

Items	Standard Deviation	Mean	Descriptive Level
Provide comprehensive course on the new organic farming technologies.	0.76	4.25	High
Able to produce a high-value crops	0.80	4.32	High
Conduct activities that enhanced entrepreneurial skills.	0.94	4.15	High
Provide financial literacy to the beneficiary.	1.28	4.00	High
Facilitate linkages that can possibly market the products.	0.98	4.10	High
Develop marketing skills.	0.89	4.21	High
Facilitates replication of all the learnings acquired by sharing to other stakeholders.	1.03	4.19	High
Provides economic empowerment for the beneficiary thru micro-financing.	1.22	3.89	High
Well-financed program that mobilizes its implementation.	1.00	4.22	High
Strengthen values formation that enable to deliver better outputs.	0.88	4.36	High
Overall	0.70	4.17	High

The top three highest items are: Strengthen values formation that enable to deliver better outputs with a mean of 4.36; Able to produce high-value crops with a mean of 4.32; Provide comprehensive course on the new organic farming technologies with a mean of 4.25. On the other hand, top three lowest items are: Provides economic empowerment for the beneficiary thru micro-financing which garnered a mean of 3.89; Provide financial literacy to the beneficiary which scored a mean of 4.00; Facilitate linkages that can possibly market the products which registered a mean of 4.10.

This supports the findings of the study of Rahmat (2011) that attainment of program objectives and learning results are critical and important to be validated through an accurate and reliable assessment, therefore, the delivery of the program implementation and assessment must be aligned with the program objectives. As a result, participants will be stimulated and responsive in doing the activities. In addition, a study conducted by Rogers (2020) suggested that program objectives should have degree of specifications, defined roles and responsibilities of participants, clear set goals for better assessment, and the frequency of data collection.

Participation of Agencies. Table 2.2 shows the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program in terms of participation of agencies. The result reveals that the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program, in terms of participation of agencies has a total mean of 3.95 which has a high level of implementation. This implies that the participation of agencies is crucial in the delivery of the program because it involves key actors which are experts in its respective fields.

Table 2.2. Level of Implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program in terms of Participation of Agencies.

Items	Standard Deviation	Mean	Descriptive Level
The Department of Agriculture supports and assists on the conduct of agro-ecosystem analysis.	1.09	4.04	High
The Department of Agriculture provides assistance on the farmers in their post-graduate plans.	1.19	3.86	High
The Department of Agriculture monitors the sustainability of the program and shares its progress report to the stakeholders.	1.02	4.06	High
The Department of Agriculture gives post-training linkages thru trading centers accredited and recommended by the Department of Agriculture.	1.00	4.01	High
The Department of Agriculture actively supports and cooperates in the implementation of the program.	0.94	4.36	High
DSWD delivers values formations, capacity and capability building and entrepreneurship training.	1.23	3.94	High
DSWD invites micro-financing organizations to lend financial aid to participants.	1.45	3.43	High
DSWD educates, assists, and tracks the farmers on their Group Sustainability Plan.	1.24	3.79	High
DSWD monitors the training program and ensures full active participation of the farmers.	1.36	3.96	High
DSWD actively supports and cooperates in the implementation of the program.	1.33	4.00	High
Overall	0.93	3.95	High

The top three highest items are: The Department of Agriculture actively supports and cooperates in the implementation of program with a mean of 4.36; The Department of Agriculture monitors the sustainability of the program and shares its progress report to its stakeholders with a mean of 4.06; The Department of Agriculture supports and assists on the conduct of agro-ecosystem analysis with a mean of 4.04. Meanwhile, the top three lowest items are: DSWD invites micro-financing organizations to lend financial aid to participants which scored a mean of 3.43; DSWD educates, assists, and tracks the farmers on their Group Sustainability Plan which registered a mean of 3.79; The Department of Agriculture provides assistance on the farmers in their post-graduate plans which collected a mean of 3.86.

The result reflects the findings on the study of United States Environmental Protection Agency (2018) that the criteria of a successful stakeholder participation require a clear purpose and objectives, clear structure and procedures, an opportunity to influence a target group, committed to be involved in the over-all process and inclusive and effective representation of the society. Furthermore, in the study of Kessler (2014), this supported that stakeholder participation strengthens the program’s legitimacy in terms of decision-making compliance and effectiveness.

Capacity Building. It is presented in Table 2.3 the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program, in terms of capacity building. The result suggests that the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program in terms of capacity building collected a total mean of 4.29 which resulted to a high level of implementation. This implies that the capacity building should also be emphasized in the implementation of the program so that the respondents will

become empowered both technical skills (planning and public presentation of their sustainability plans) and communication skills (how to deal with different offices and people in a professional level).

Table 2.3. Level of Implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program in terms of Capacity Building

Items	Standard Deviation	Mean	Descriptive Level
The agro-ecosystem analysis (AESAs) teaches and allows the participants to observe, monitor and record significant findings on the crop development.	1.07	4.29	High
The financial literacy was facilitated by experts and enables to provide education on income sustainability.	1.27	4.04	High
The Sustainability Forum trains the participants on the guidelines in program cropping, production planning, goal setting, marketing, and sustainability.	0.89	4.28	High
Helps formulate a SMART Sustainability Plan.	0.99	4.26	High
The Sustainability Plans are presented in various agencies as proposal.	0.99	3.97	High
Encourages strong community ownership and builds teamwork to achieve desired outcomes.	0.86	4.49	High
The basic concepts on packaging, pricing and product display of fresh produce were demonstrated and applied.	1.13	3.88	High
The culmination program enables to showcase the crop harvests in the public.	0.77	4.53	Very High
The acquired knowledge from the program can be shared, replicated, and adopted by others.	0.78	4.57	Very High
The over-all program was helpful and useful in attainment of food security and sustainability.	0.74	4.61	Very High
Overall	0.74	4.29	High

The top three highest items are: The over-all program was helpful and useful in the attainment of food security and sustainability with a mean of 4.61; The acquired knowledge from the program can be shared, replicated, and adopted by others with a mean of 4.57; The culmination program enables to showcase the crop harvests in the public. Conversely, the top three lowest items are: The basic concepts on packaging, pricing and product display of fresh produce were demonstrated and applied which scored a mean of 3.88; The Sustainability Plans are presented in various agencies as proposal which registered a mean of 3.97; The financial literacy was facilitated by experts and enables to provide education on income sustainability which garnered a mean of 4.04.

The result espouses the study conducted by United Nations Development Programme (2016) that the main targeted result of capacity development is transformation. Transformation must be carried out in a sustained period; hence, this should not only be a performance task but rather changing perspectives and behavior. The finding reflects also the research conducted by International Committee of the Red Cross (2013) which elaborated the four key factors of capacity building which are institutional development, financial resource development, human resource development and national societal programs. These components are co-equal and integrated accordingly to help empowering individuals especially those who are vulnerable.

Test of Difference in the Level of Implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program when the Respondents are grouped according to Profile of the Respondent

This section shows the test of difference on the level of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program when grouped according to profile of the respondent.

Educational Attainment. As presented in Table 3 is the result of test of difference in the level of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program, according to highest educational attainment. The result reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of “Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan” Program when grouped according to highest educational attainment with the total f-value of 2.44 and p-value of 0.09 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant and the rejection of alternative hypothesis.

In the study performed by Economic and Social Research Council (2014), it suggested that the level of education is one of the strongest outcome predictors in program implementation. However, the study corroborates that regardless of educational attainment obtained, most of the people are satisfied on what they have accomplished, therefore, they share equal footing in the program implementation. On the other hand, the research findings of International Panel on Social

Progress (2021) supported the argument that education is essential mobilizing tool to attain social equality and higher chances of social inclusion, or when not present or insufficiently accessed, the higher the risks of social injustice and social exclusion.

Table 3. Significant Difference in the Level of Implementation of "Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan" Program when the Respondents are grouped according to Educational Attainment.

Educational Attainment	College	High School	Elementary	F-Value	P-Value	Decision
Attainment of the Program Objectives	4.36	4.05	4.60	1.94	0.15	Not Significant
Participation of Agencies	4.16	4.16	3.79	2.69	0.07	Not Significant
Capacity Building	4.47	4.17	4.80	1.77	0.17	Not Significant
Overall	4.33	4.01	4.80	2.44	0.09	Not Significant

Attainment of program objectives as an indicator of educational attainment as manifested in the f-value of 1.94 with a p-value of 0.15 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This means that attainment of program objectives is implemented equally regardless of educational attainment.

Participation of agencies as an indicator of educational attainment as reflected in the f-value 2.69 with a p-value of 0.07 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This implies that participation of agencies is implemented in the same manner regardless of educational attainment.

Capacity building as an indicator of educational attainment as disclosed in f-value of 1.77 with a p-value of 0.17 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This proves that capacity building is implemented across all regardless of educational attainment.

Years in Farming. In Table 4, the result shows the test of difference in the level of implementation of "Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan" Program when grouped according to years in farming. The result reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of "Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan" Program when grouped according to years in farming with the total f-value of 0.27 and p-value of 0.75 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant and the rejection of alternative hypothesis.

Table 4. Significant Difference in the Level of Implementation of "Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan" Program when the Respondents are grouped according to Years in Farming.

Years in Farming	10 years and below	11-20 years	21 years and above	F-Value	P-Value	Decision
Attainment of Program Objectives	4.17	4.21	4.09	0.08	0.92	Not Significant
Participation of Agencies	3.97	4.10	3.62	0.77	0.46	Not Significant
Capacity Building	4.27	4.39	4.26	0.10	0.90	Not Significant
Overall	4.14	4.23	3.99	0.27	0.75	Not Significant

In the study of United Nations Development Programme (2016), program implementation and evaluation are reflected no significance to those individual skills, experiences, and capabilities. These traits may be either gained from formal or informal approaches such as length of practical experience and thru observation. Meanwhile, in the data findings of World Bank (2021) argued that skills development may lessen unemployment rate, alleviate productivity, and can enhance the quality of living that may result to be socio-economically able individuals.

Attainment of program objectives as an indicator of years in farming as manifested in the f-value of 0.08 with a p-value of 0.92 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This means that implementation of attainment of program objectives is alike regardless of years in farming.

Participation of agencies as an indicator of years in farming as reflected in the f-value 0.77 with a p-value of 0.46 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This implies that participation of agencies is implemented in the same manner regardless of years in farming.

Capacity building as an indicator of years in farming as disclosed in f-value of 0.10 with a p-value of 0.90. The result is not significant. This proves that capacity building is implemented across all regardless of years in farming.

Employment. In Table 5, it discusses the result of test of difference in the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when grouped according to employment. The results reflect that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when grouped according to employment. The result reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when grouped according to employment with the total f-value of 0.77 and p-value of 0.46 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant and the rejection of alternative hypothesis.

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Level of Implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when the Respondents are grouped according to Employment.

Employment	Government	Self-Employed	Private	F-Value	P-Value	Decision
Attainment of the Program Objectives	4.25	4.25	4.00	1.05	0.35	Not Significant
Participation of Agencies	3.75	4.05	3.92	0.58	0.55	Not Significant
Capacity Building	4.35	4.42	4.06	1.73	0.18	Not Significant
Overall	4.12	4.24	3.99	0.77	0.46	Not Significant

According to the study performed by International Development Association (2021), it is argued that employment in line with program implementation is critical in stopping immoderate poverty, hence, poor, and marginalized individuals who have no assets, see employment as a venue to escape socio-economic deprivation. On the other hand, Khan (2013) research study contested that employment growth in relation to program productivity can hasten economic development rate. The link factors between employment and poverty eradication underly on program policies and implementation on increasing income, increasing in self-employment efficacy, higher productivity rate obtained from self-employment and increase in the economic flow of input, process, and output. The collective results of these may decrease the effects of poverty.

Attainment of program objectives as an indicator of employment as manifested in the f-value of 1.05 with a p-value of 0.35 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This means that attainment of program objectives is implemented regardless of employment.

Participation of agencies as an indicator of employment as reflected in the f-value 0.58 with a p-value of 0.55 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This implies that participation of agencies is implemented in the same manner regardless of employment.

Capacity building as an indicator of employment as disclosed in f-value of 1.73 with a p-value of 0.18 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant. This proves that capacity building is implemented across all regardless of employment status.

“*Kabuhayang Angat Sa Pilipinas*” (KASAPI) Program Metrics Framework

The “*Kabuhayang Angat sa Pilipinas*” Program is the proposed enhancement metrics framework which is the result from integration of all the component actors and plans in its full implementation. The component actors are the partnership and collaboration of existing partners such as SM Foundation Incorporated as the core lead, Banco De Oro, regional offices of Department of Social Welfare and Development (DTI), and Department of Agriculture (DA).

In addition, “*Kabuhayang Angat sa Pilipinas*” Program proposes a partnership with the new agencies: Technical Skills Development Authority (TESDA), Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), Cooperative Development Authority (CDA) and on the local government unit represented by City Agricultural Office. Also, there will be five identified Key Result Areas.

Training and Course Management. The activities under this Key Result Area are to design and provide course training on the organic farming technique, inorganic farming technique and mixed method farming techniques from City Agriculture Office, and conduct orientation and facilitate commencement of the training. Also, success indicators are the training and course management will be designed, crafted, and implemented by experts in partnership with both private and public agencies, and the facilitation of the training proper shall be discussed on the first day of orientation. The person involved are SM personnel, City Agriculture Office, Macondry and Harbest Philippines. Lastly, the proposed budget is Php 35,000.

Financial Literacy and Management. The activities under this KRA are to provide basic financial management courses facilitated by experts from DTI and BDO, and the participants are expected to formulate financial plan. Furthermore, the

success indicators are the financial experts will provide lecture and trainings on the financial literacy and management aspect, and the participants can be able to identify key points on the financial literacy that can be used in the formulation of financial plan. The proposed budget is Php 25,000.

Entrepreneurship and Capacity Building Seminar. The activities under this KRA are to conduct entrepreneurship courses and essential business key concepts, activates team building, and coaching session. Moreover, the success indicators are the experts will introduce lecture and trainings on the key business and entrepreneurship concepts, 100% cooperation and participation in the team building and 90% to 100% of the participants will feel empowered and dignified. The persons involved are DTI, TESDA, SM Foundation and Cooperative Development Authority. The proposed budget is Php 25,000.

Basic Business Plan and Proposal Techniques. The activities under this KRA are to design and craft an effective business plan or marketing plan, and the participants are expected to create a business proposal and/or marketing plan. Further, success indicators are experts will provide lecture and trainings in the creation of business or marketing plan, and the participants can be able to identify salient points and create business or marketing plan. The persons involved will be from SM Foundation, DTI, and Cooperative Development Authority. The proposed budget is Php 25,000.

Learning Integration and Immersion. The activities under this KRA are graduates expected to replicate and share learnings in their community, and fully integrate the key points on food security. Moreover, success indicators are fully adoption and integration of the learnings, and 100% participants will graduate from the program. The persons involved are SM Foundation, Department of Trade and Industry, City Agriculture Office, TESDA, and BDO. The proposed budget is Php 25,000. Overall, the total proposed budget is Php 140,000.00 per program implementation.

Lastly, “*Kabuhayang Angat sa Pilipinas*” Program aims to achieve 90% to 100% success indicators at the end of the program and these are: efficient and effective training course management thru an assessment and evaluation tools, acquired financial literacy knowledge that will help them to a sound financial decision-making, developed their entrepreneurial skills and boost their dignity and morale, performed a business plan and proposal presentation, and integrated learning and skills that will manifest a strong leadership and sense of community immersion.

Table 6 shows the formulation of the enhancement program of the existing “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program based on the results. The enhancement program will be called as “*Kabuhayang Angat sa Pilipinas*” or KASAPI Program.

Table 6. “*Kabuhayang Angat Sa Pilipinas*” KASAPI Program Metrics Framework

Key Result Area	Activities	Success Indicators	Person Involved	Source/Budget
Training and Course Management	Designs and provides course training on the organic farming technique, inorganic farming, and mixed-method techniques from CAO. (A1)	The training and course management will be designed, crafted, and implemented by experts in partnership with both private and public agencies. The need for review, assessment and evaluation of past trainings conducted is essential and critical in this area.	1.SM Personnel 2.City Agriculture’s Office 3.Macondry and Harbest Philippines	Php 10,000
	Conducts orientation and facilitate commencement of the training. (A2)	The facilitation of the training proper shall be discussed on the first day of orientation to set the program objectives, to set expectations, competencies, and outcomes at the end of the program.	1.SM Personnel 2.City Agriculture’s Office 3.Macondry and Harbest Philippines	Php 25,000

Financial Literacy and Management	Provides basic financial management courses facilitated by experts from DTI and BDO. (A1)	The financial experts will provide lecture and trainings on the financial literacy and management aspect.	1.DTI 2. BDO Bank	Php 15,000
	The participants are expected to formulate Financial Plan that will be presented as proposal. (A2)	The participants can be able to identify key points on the financial literacy and can formulate, prepare, and execute Financial Plan.	1.DTI 2. BDO Bank	Php 10,000
Entrepreneurship and Capacity Building Seminar	Conducts entrepreneurship courses and essential business key concepts. (A1)	The experts will introduce lecture and trainings on the key business and entrepreneurship concepts.	1.DTI 2. TESDA 3.SM Foundation 4.Cooperative Development Authority	Php 10,000
	Provides capacity building thru a TEAM BUILDING mechanism to increase self-morale. (A2)	The participants are expected to participate and cooperate on the team building activities and 90% may feel empowered.	1.DTI 2. TESDA 3.SM Foundation 4.Cooperative Development Authority	Php 10,000
Entrepreneurship and Capacity Building Seminar	Coaching session (A3)	90% to 100% of the participants may feel empowered.	1.DTI 2. TESDA 3.SM Foundation 4.Cooperative Development Authority	Php 5,000
Basic Business Plan and Proposal Techniques	Designs and crafts an effective Business Plan or Marketing Plan. (A1)	The experts will provide lecture and trainings on Business Plan and Marketing Plan.	1.SM Foundation 2. DTI 3. Cooperative Development Authority	Php 10,000
	The participants are expected to formulate Business Proposal or Marketing Plan that will be presented as proposal. (A2)	The participants can be able to identify salient points on the Business Plan/Marketing Plan and can formulate, prepare, and execute proposal.	1.SM Foundation 2. DTI 3. Cooperative Development Authority	Php 15,000
Learning Integration and Immersion	The graduates are expected to replicate learnings, able to form association, and fully integrate the key points of Food Security in the community. (A1)	90% to 100% of the graduates can be able to replicate, share and adopt the learnings acquired from the program.	1.SM Foundation 2. DTI 3. CAO 4.TESDA 5. BDO	Php 5,000
	Public Presentation and Graduation Ceremony. (A2)	90% to 100% of the graduates can be able to replicate, share and adopt the learnings acquired from the program.	1.SM Foundation 2. DTI 3. CAO 4.TESDA 5. BDO	Php 25,000

In the study of Conrey et al. (2012), it is stated that enhancement program should include four basic components that will dictate consumer and market behavior, and these are: recruitment of a state-wide cooperative extension staff to help in the promotion of farmers' program and efforts; there should be an intense collaboration and integration with all the state-agencies concerned; intensification of local community context capacity building skills; and the distribution of the latest innovation and trends about nutrition education.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary of the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the data analysis.

Summary

The study aimed to assess the “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program on farmers in Davao City. Particularly, the study sought to answer the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program in terms of attainment of program objectives, participation of agencies and capacity building. Moreover, it aimed to find out if there is a significant difference in the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when the respondents are grouped according to educational attainment, years in farming and employment. The study is a correlational-comparative research design. The primary data were administered and collected through an online survey questionnaire.

The study reveals that majority of the respondents were college level/graduate, with one to ten years in farming experience, and dominantly self-employed. Moreover, the study shows that the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program on farmers in Davao City in terms of attainment of program objectives, participation of agencies and capacity building were highly implemented. Furthermore, the findings reveal that the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when the respondents are grouped by educational attainment, years in farming and employment has no significant difference. Finally, an enhancement program metrics framework was created for “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program.

Conclusion

This study inferred that majority of the respondents were college level/graduate, with one to ten years in farming experience and self-employed. Also, this study concluded that the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program in terms of attainment of program objectives, participation of agencies, and capacity building were highly implemented. Also, it is found out that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program when the respondents are grouped according to educational attainment, years in farming, and capacity building. An enhancement program metrics framework was created for “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program.

Recommendation

The following are the recommendations made on the bases of findings and conclusions:

The Department of Agriculture may review its existing provisions in its partnership with private organizations in the implementation and post-evaluation of the program. The national agency may appoint City Agriculture Office as the main focal point in the planning and coordination phase of the program in the local government level and may implement the enhancement program metrics framework of this study.

The Department of Social Welfare and Development may act as the “nurturing” agency in the implementation of “*Kabalikat sa Kabuhayan*” Program. They could be pillars to encourage and motivate the farmers, especially those who are in marginalized sectors, to push and perform well. And ensure post activity outcomes are consistently monitored and measured. The office of DSWD could act also as the “middle agency” in connecting the farmers to various government offices such the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) and Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) for national competency skills and assessment.

The SM Foundation Incorporated may use the enhancement program metrics framework that could help them re-think on the possible ways to integrate the findings of the study and create assessment tools and techniques.

The farmers may benefit in the enhancement program metric framework for this could aid them in better performance before, during and after the duration of the program course. This could give them justification in their roles and could also dignify their worth.

The future researchers may undertake this kind of study or related study as an additional literature. This could be replicated by other organizations that has a similar program, Moreover, this study would encourage them to look also on other factors that affect program implementation and can suggest more recommendations based on empirical data obtained.

REFERENCES

- [1] Asian Development Bank. (2018). Leading Factors of Success and Failure in Asian Development Bank Urban Sanitation Project. May 10, 2021. <https://www.adb.org/documents/leading-factors-success-and-failure-asian-development-bank-urban-sanitation-projects>
- [2] Bureau of Internal Revenue. (2019). Income tax. February 25, 2021. <https://www.bir.gov.ph/index.php/tax-information/income-tax.html>
- [3] Charvat, J. (2013). Project management methodologies selecting, implementing, and supporting methodologies and processes for project. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [4] Civil Service Commission. (2014). CSC: Mandate. March 9, 2020. <http://www.csc.gov.ph/2014-02-20-02-22-48/2014-02-20-02-29-25.html>
- [5] Commission on Higher Education. (2021). CHED: Vision, mission and mandate. March 5, 2021. <https://ched.gov.ph/ched/>
- [6] Conrey, E. J. et al. (2012). Integrated program enhancements increased utilization of farmers' market nutrition program. Community and International Nutrition Research Communication. 1841-1844.
- [7] Crano, W.D., Brewer, M.B. and Lac, A. (2014). Principles and methods of social research. Routledge. ISBN 131766 6070.
- [8] Davao City Investment Promotion Center. (2021). May 13, 2021. <https://invest.davaocity.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Davao-City-Agribusiness-Industry-Profile.pdf>
- [9] Department of Agriculture. (2021). Department of Agriculture: Mandate. March 5, 2021. <https://www.da.gov.ph/mandate/>
- [10] Department of Education. (2020). DepEd: Vision, mission, core values, and mandate. March 5, 2021. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/about-deped/vision-mission-core-values-and-mandate/>
- [11] Department of Labor and Employment. (2017). The labor code of the Philippines, renumbered, DOLE edition. March 5, 2021. https://www.dole.gov.ph/php_assets/uploads/2017/11/LaborCode_ofthePhilippines20171.pdf
- [12] Department of Social Welfare and Development. (2021). Department of Social Welfare and Development: Citizen's charter. March 5, 2021. <https://www.dswd.gov.ph/>
- [13] Disenza, R. & Forman, J. B. (2013). Seven causes of project failure: how to recognize them and how to initiate project recovery. Paper presented at PMI® Global Congress 2007—North America, Atlanta, GA. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- [14] Durlak, J.A. (2013). Why Program Implementation is Important. Journal of Prevention & Intervention Community, 17(2):5-8. http://dx.doi.org/10.1300/J005v17n02_02
- [15] Economic and Social Research Council. (2014). The wellbeing effect of education. Retrieved from <https://esrc.ukri.org/news-events-and-publications/evidence-briefings/the-wellbeing-effect-of-education/#:~:text=Key%20findings,less%20hostile%20attitudes%20towards%20immigrants.>
- [16] Esser, F. & Vliegthart, R. (2017). Comparative research methods. April 23, 2021. https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/9781118901731.i_ecrm0035
- [17] Food and Agriculture Organization United Nations. (2018). Transforming food and agriculture to achieve SDGs. FAO UN. ISBN: 978-92-5-130998-8.
- [18] Freeman, E. R. (2012). Divergent stakeholder theory. Academy of management review, 233-236. ISSN: 0363-7425.
- [19] Frey, B.B. (2018). The SAGE Encyclopedia of Educational Research, Measurement, and Evaluation. SAGE Publication. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781506326139.n636>
- [20] Hamilton, J. (2012). Primary and Secondary Sources: ABDO Publishing Company.
- [21] Hayes, A. (2021). Investopedia: Demographics. May 25, 2021. <https://investopedia.com/terms/d/demographics.asp>

- [22] International Committee of the Red Cross. (2020). Framework for National Society Capacity Building. May 14, 2021. <https://www.nzdl.org>
- [23] International Development Association. (2021). Jobs and economic transformation. May1,2021.<http://ida.worldbank.org/theme/jobs-and-economic-transformation>
- [24] International Labour Office Statistics. (2012). Glossary of statistical terms. March18,2021.<https://ilostat.ilo.org/resources/concepts-and-definitions/glossary/#E>
- [25] International Labour Office. (2012). Updating the international standards of occupations (ISCO), Draft ISCO-08 Group Definitions: Occupations in Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries. March 16,2021.<https://www.ilo.org/public/english/bureau/stat/isco/docs/d2b.pdf>
- [26] International Labour Organization (2021). Project evaluation. April 23, 2021.https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---exrel/documents/genericdocument/wcms_172679.pdf
- [27] International Panel on Social Progress. (2021). How Can Education Promote Social Progress? May 14, 2021. <https://www.comment.ipsp.org>
- [28] Kessler, B. L. (2014). Stakeholder Participation: A Synthesis of Current Literature. May 13, 2021. https://nmsmarineprotectedareas.blob.core.windows.net/marineprotectedareasprod/media/archive/pdf/publications/Stakeholder_Synthesis.pdf
- [29] Khan, A.R. (2013). Growth, Employment and Poverty: An Analysis of the Vital Nexus based on Some Recent UNDO and ILO/SIDA Studies. ISBN 92-2-117835-8. May 23, 2021. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/ed_emp/documents/publication/wcms_120683.pdf
- [30] Laerd Statistics. (2018). One-way ANOVA. May 1, 2020. <https://statistics.laerd.com/statistical-guides/one-way-anova-statistical-guide.php>
- [31] Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences. (2019). Survey Guidelines: Socio-demographic variables. May 25, 2021. <https://www.gesis.org/en/gesis-survey-guidelines/instruments/survey-instruments/socio-demographic-variables>
- [32] Murray, J. (2020). What does it mean to be self-employed?. The Balance Small Business. February 19, 2021. <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/what-does-it-mean-to-be-self-employed-398471>
- [33] National Economic Development Authority and Department of Budget and Management. (2015). National Evaluation Policy Framework of the Philippines. May 10, 2021. <https://nep.neda.gov.ph/document/NEDA-DBM%20Joint%20Memorandum%20Circular%20No.%202015-01%20National%20Evaluation%20Policy%20Framework%20of%20the%20Philippines.pdf>
- [34] National Economic Development Authority. (2017). Philippine Development Plan 2017-2022 Abridged Version. Pasig City, Philippines. ISSN:2243-7576.
- [35] National Geographic. (2020). Agriculture. January 20, 2021. <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/encyclopedia/agriculture/>
- [36] Prosovac, E.J. and Carey, R.G. (1997). Program evaluation: methods and case studies. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [37] Rahmat, R.A.A.O.K. (2011). Achievement of program outcomes using assessment plan. procedia-social and behavioral science, 18, 87-93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.05.013>
- [38] Rogers, G. (2020). Program Educational Objectives and Student Outcomes: Same but Different. May 13, 2021. https://www.abet.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Objectives_Outcomes-09.09.20.pdf
- [39] Sharpe, G. (2011). A review of program theory and theory-based evaluations. American International Journal of Contemporary Research.1(3),72-75.http://aijernet.com/journals/Vol_1_No_3_November_2011/10.pdf
- [40] Sidani, S. and Sechrest, L. (1999). Putting program theory into operation. American Journal of Evaluation, 20 (2), 227-238.

- [41] SM Foundation Incorporated. (2018). SMIC sustainability report 2018. April 5, 2020. <https://www.sm-foundation.org/>
- [42] Sy, M., O'Leary, N., Nagraj, S., El-Awaisi, A., O'Carroll, V., & Xyrichis, A. (2020). Doing interprofessional research in the COVID-19 era: a discussion paper. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, 1-7.
- [43] Technical Skills and Development Authority. (2020). TESDA: Vision, mission, value and quality statement. March 9, 2021. <https://www.tesda.gov.ph/About/TESDA/11>
- [44] Torrentira, M.C. (2020). Online data collection as adaptation in conducting quantitative and qualitative research during the covid-19 pandemic, *7* (11), 78-87. <http://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v7i11.3336>
- [45] United Nations Educational, Scientific, Cultural and Organization Institute for Statistics. (2020). Educational attainment. March 9, 2021. <http://uis.unesco.org/en/topic/educational-attainment>
- [46] United Nations Development Program. (2016). Capacity development: a UNDP primer. April 23, 2021 https://www.undp.org/content/dam/aplaws/publication/en/publications/capacity-development/capacity-development-a-undp-primer/CDG_PrimerReport_final_web.pdf
- [47] United States Department of Health and Human Services (2021). Design and implementation: the contribution of implementation science. March 9, 2021. <https://childcareta.acf.hhs.gov/systemsbuilding/systems-guides/design-and-implementation/contribution-implementation-science>
- [48] United States Environmental Protection Agency. (2018). Public participation guide: introduction to public participation. April 23, 2021. <https://www.epa.gov/international-cooperation/public-participation-guide-introduction-public-participation>
- [49] World Bank (2021). Understanding poverty: Skills Development. May 1, 2021. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/skillsdevelopment>